

Milestone:

M4.1: Expansion of ELITMa (ELIXIR Training Programme in Management) with modules focused on ELIXIR Node Services Provision and Greening of research infrastructure operations

Lead Participant:

UOCHB

Author:

Luciana Peixoto (BioData.pt, PT), Anna Strachotova (UOCHB, CZ)

Due:

31 January 2026 (24)

Date Of Completion:

14/01/2026

Means of Verification

- <https://f1000research.com/posters/14-577>
- <https://f1000research.com/posters/14-782>
- <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/training/elitma>

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No delay

Project participants & others

Luciana Peixoto (biodata.pt, PT), Anna Strachotova (UOCHB, CZ), David Dolan (UiB, NO), Bengt Persson (UU, SE), Celia van Gelder, Mijke Jetten (Health-RI, NL), Wei Gu (PNED, LU), Brane Leskošek (UL, SI), Lucy Poveda (SIB, CH), Balázs Győrffy, (TTK, HU), Munazah Andrabi & Xénia Perez (UNIMAN, UK) Corinne Martin (ELIXIR Hub, IO), Dan Ben-Avraham (WEIZMANN, IL), Hedi Peterson (UT, EE), Fran Borovečki (UZSM, HR), Colm Ryan (UCD, IE).

Next action steps

- Carbon Footprint module implementation and delivery (1st edition online)
- Conversations with the Nodes to establish how ELITMa is perceived, narratives will be collected
- Connecting with WP2 - explore ELITMa Module related to the impact indicators they have developed.
- Adding ELITMa modules materials in TeSS

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